

Squeezing Out the Achievable Information Rate From Coherent QAM Systems Through Amplitude Modulation of CPE-Pilots

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Abstract: We propose to perform amplitude modulation over DSP pilots commonly employed for carrier-phase estimation, utilizing the extra information rate to carry additional FEC overhead. For moderate pilot overheads of 3-6%, we demonstrate SNR gains in the range of 0.6-1.7 dB. © 2021 The Author(s)

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1. Introduction

The ever-increasing demand for high data-rate optical systems has led to the development of extremely efficient modulation formats and transmission schemes, in which the achievable information rate (IR) is optimized close to the ultimate Shannon limit of spectral efficiency (SE) [1]. Nevertheless, in order to guarantee the full DSP functionality of the coherent transceiver, a residual overhead of pilot symbols is commonly required [2]. In particular, it is quite common to allocate some non-negligible pilot overhead to aid on the carrier-phase estimation (CPE) DSP subsystem, in order to guarantee a high-performance and cycle-slip-free DSP operation [3, 4]. However, the overhead allocated for CPE-pilots results in a waste of transmitted IR, leading to a suboptimal utilization of the channel capacity.

In this paper, we propose to perform amplitude modulation over CPE-pilots to enhance the IR of the transmitted signal, which is then utilized to enhance the forward-error correction (FEC) coding gain. Theoretical, simulation and experimental results demonstrate that sizeable SNR gains can be obtained, while maintaining the operating net SE.

2. On the Implications of Amplitude Modulation over CPE-Pilots

Denoting P_k as the k -th transmitted pilot symbol, and \hat{P}_k as its corresponding received symbol, the working principle of pilot-based CPE is to directly evaluate the phase difference between P_k and \hat{P}_k as,

$$\hat{\phi}_{\text{PN}}(k) = -\arg(P_k \cdot \hat{P}_k^*), \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{\phi}_{\text{PN}}(k)$ is the estimated phase noise at time instant k .

The IR in bits per channel use (bpcu) per polarization of a uniformly-distributed M -QAM signal with FEC coding and CPE-pilots is given by,

$$\text{IR} = \log_2(M)R_{\text{FEC}}R_{\text{PIL}}, \quad (2)$$

where R_{FEC} denotes the FEC code rate and R_{PIL} is the CPE pilot rate. Most commonly, the CPE pilots are in the form of “QPSK-like” symbols, typically inserted either at the outer QAM symbols or at the average QAM energy, as depicted in Fig. 1. Instead of following this convention, let us now consider that the CPE pilot symbols can take any value over the diagonals of the square QAM template, i.e. any QAM symbol with a phase component in the form $(2n-1)\frac{\pi}{4}$, as indicated by the red crosses (\times) in Fig. 1. Without prejudice of the phase estimation rule of expression (1), it then becomes apparent that the amplitude of the CPE-pilots offers an additional degree of freedom to carry information, providing an extra IR, IR_{PIL} , which is given by,

$$\text{IR}_{\text{PIL}} = \log_2\left(\frac{\sqrt{M}}{2}\right)(1 - R_{\text{PIL}}). \quad (3)$$

The application of expression (3) to 16QAM, 64QAM and 256QAM is shown in Fig. 2a. For typical pilot rates of 31/32 (3.125% overhead), it can be seen that an extra 0.1 bits/symbol can be obtained with 256QAM modulation. Further IR gains can be obtained in systems that utilize lower pilot rates, achieving roughly 0.4 bits/symbol for a pilot-rate of 7/8 (12.5% overhead). Let us now consider that this extra IR can be used to allocate additional FEC parity bits, thus enabling to reduce the overall FEC rate (i.e. increase the FEC overhead), while maintaining the same

Fig. 1: Example of CPE-pilots placement on a 64QAM constellation following different strategies: pilots placed at the outer QAM symbols (\square); pilots placed at the average QAM energy (\blacksquare); and pilots with QAM amplitude modulation (\times).

Fig. 2: Theoretical analysis of the impact of CPE-pilots amplitude modulation. a) extra IR embedded within CPE-pilots; b) impact on the FEC rate when starting from a baseline $R_{\text{FEC}} = 5/6$; c) theoretical SNR gain associated with the decrease of FEC rate enabled by CPE-pilots modulation.

net SE. It can be demonstrated that the new FEC rate, R'_{FEC} , enabled by CPE-pilot modulation is given by,

$$R'_{\text{FEC}} = R_{\text{FEC}} - \frac{\text{IR}_{\text{PIL}}}{\log_2(M)R_{\text{PIL}}}. \quad (4)$$

The corresponding relationship between R_{PIL} and R'_{FEC} is illustrated in Fig. 2b, where a baseline $R_{\text{FEC}} = 5/6$ and $R_{\text{PIL}} = 1$ is considered. Naturally, the increased FEC overhead enabled by CPE-pilots modulation will translate into effective SNR gains. In order to quantify this SNR gain, let us consider for simplicity the use of an ideal coding scheme, such that threshold NGMI for error-free communication is equal to the FEC rate, $\text{NGMI}_{\text{th}} = R_{\text{FEC}}$. Resorting to the NGMI computation algorithm proposed in [5], the corresponding theoretical results are depicted in Fig. 2c, where it can be observed that gains exceeding 0.5 dB can be achieved for moderate pilot overheads of 5–6%.

The above theoretical analysis is based on the premise that the amplitude modulation of CPE-pilots will produce a negligible impact on the phase estimation performance. In order to validate this assumption, we performed Monte Carlo simulations whose results are presented in Table 1, indicating the required SNR associated with the use of different strategies for the placement of CPE-pilots over 64QAM and 256QAM templates, while also considering different pilot rates and different combined laser linewidths. An interesting first conclusion is that the use of CPE-pilots in the outer QAM symbols (solid blue lines) becomes largely sub-optimal as the pilot-rate decreases. This is due to the increase in the average energy of the transmitted signal, which requires higher transmitted power to keep the same operating SNR. In that regard, the placement of CPE-pilots at the average energy (dashed red lines) of the QAM constellation is a more adequate solution when the utilized pilot overhead exceeds 3–6%. Most importantly, it can be seen that the application of amplitude modulation over CPE-pilots (dotted black lines) yields only < 0.1 dB performance penalty compared to the average energy strategy, even for extreme combined laser linewidths of 1 MHz, which confirms the potentiality to extract effective SNR gains from the extra IR provided by CPE-pilots modulation.

3. Experimental Validation

The experimental setup utilized for the validation of the previously discussed theoretical and simulation results is presented in Fig. 3a. The optical carrier and local oscillator are generated by external cavity lasers (ECL)

Table 1: Impact of the CPE-pilots position on the required SNR for different pilot-rates and combined laser linewidths.

Fig. 3: Experimental results. a) laboratory setup: OBPF - optical band-pass filter; OSA - optical spectrum analyzer; b) 16QAM B2B characterization at 60 Gbaud (\circ); c) 64QAM B2B characterization at 30 Gbaud (∇) and 60 Gbaud (\square); d) SNR gains enabled by CPE-pilots modulation.

operating at 1550 nm with roughly 100 kHz linewidth. The electrical signal is synthesized by an arbitrary waveform generator (AWG) with 120 Gsa/s and 45 GHz bandwidth. A dual-polarization (DP) IQ modulator with ~ 35 GHz bandwidth followed by a booster EDFA is utilized at the optical transmitter. The operating OSNR is measured by an optical spectrum analyzer (OSA) and set through EDFA-generated noise loading, whose power is controlled by an electronically-actuated variable optical attenuator (VOA). Out-of-band noise is filtered by 200 GHz optical band-pass filters (OBPF). A coherent receiver with 40 GHz bandwidth performs the optical-to-electrical conversion and sends the I and Q components to a real-time oscilloscope operating at 100 Gsa/s on 4 ports, with 33 GHz bandwidth. Receiver-side DSP includes a 5-taps CMA followed by frequency estimation and pilot-based CPE. Finally, after a 51 taps LMS equalizer the signal is demapped and the NGMI is evaluated. Figures 3b and 3c show the back-to-back (B2B) characterizations obtained with 16QAM (60 Gbaud) and 64QAM (30 Gbaud and 60 Gbaud), respectively. In the 60 Gbaud 16QAM case (Fig. 3b, solid blue line, \circ), we observe a B2B penalty of 2.5 dB for $\text{NGMI}_{\text{th}} = 5/6$. In addition, we also observe that the gap between the experimental and theoretical curves is approximately constant within the NGMIs of interest, i.e. in the range of 0.78 and 0.83, in accordance with R_{pil} and R_{FEC}' dependence shown in Fig. 2b. For that reason, the experimental SNR gain shown in Fig. 3d very nearly follows the theoretical expectation for the 16QAM case. Considering a pilot-rate of 15/16 (6.25% overhead), an SNR gain of ~ 0.3 dB is achieved. A similar behavior is observed for the 30 Gbaud 64QAM scenario (Fig. 3c, solid green line, ∇), where the experimental SNR gains in Fig. 3d are also well matched with the theoretical curve. Let us now analyze the 60 Gbaud 64QAM results (Fig. 3c, solid red line, \square). Due to the imperfect frequency response and limited vertical resolution in the AWG and oscilloscope, the B2B penalty at $\text{NGMI}_{\text{th}} = 5/6$ is substantially increased to about 7.3 dB. Consequently, it can also be observed that the gap between the theoretical and experimental curves gets significantly narrower as we lower the threshold NGMI, reaching 5.2 dB at $\text{NGMI}_{\text{th}} = 0.8$ and 3.7 dB at $\text{NGMI}_{\text{th}} = 0.75$. This is a typical behavior in systems that are operating close to the NGMI saturation point, which might happen in practical transceivers when the target bit-rates are pushed to the limits. The logical consequence of such behavior is that a significant SNR gain can be obtained by increasing the FEC overhead and thus lowering the threshold NGMI. However, in traditional transmission systems this cannot be done without reducing the net bit-rate. By utilizing the proposed feature of CPE-pilots modulation, the extra IR allocated within the pilot symbols can be transferred to an additional FEC overhead, thus lowering the operating NGMI threshold without compromising the net bit-rate. Consequently, substantial gains can be achieved in these systems, as shown in Fig. 3d, where 0.6 dB gain is observed at a typical pilot-rate of 31/32 and 1.7 dB gain is achieved at a pilot-rate of 15/16.

4. Conclusions

We have proposed the use of amplitude modulation over CPE-pilots to enhance the achievable IR in square M -QAM systems employing pilot-based CPE. By transferring the IR obtained from pilot modulation to an extra FEC overhead, theoretical and experimental analyses have confirmed the possibility of obtaining SNR gains that scale with both the constellation order and pilot overhead. In systems operating close to the NGMI saturation point, these gains can be further amplified. In a 60 Gbaud 64QAM system, we demonstrated up to 1.7 dB gain at a moderate pilot-rate of 15/16.

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